

**SIXTH NORTH AMERICAN SYRIAC SYMPOSIUM
“SYRIAC ENCOUNTERS”**

Dear Symposium Participants,

It is a pleasure to welcome you to Duke University and Durham, North Carolina, for the Sixth North American Syriac Symposium!

Please take a moment to review some important reminders:

- All events (excluding the opening events Sunday evening and the dinners Monday and Tuesday) will be held in two adjoining buildings located immediately east of Duke Chapel: the Gray Building (Duke University Religion Department) and the Westbrook Building (Duke Divinity School).
- Lunches and dinners are included for registered participants. You may purchase breakfast at the Washington Duke Inn or partake of muffins and coffee in the York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor, 8:30 – 8:55a, Monday through Wednesday).
- The York Reading Room will host a Book Pavilion where titles from Gorgias Press and Peeters Publishers will be on display.
- Concurrent paper sessions are designated A, B, and C and will be held in three new lecture halls in the Divinity School’s Westbrook Building: Room 0016=A; 0012=B; and 0013=C. (If your paper includes an A/V presentation, please be sure to alert one of the Symposium organizers in advance.)
- All papers will begin and end on time. In order to allow five minutes for discussion (as well as an opportunity for participants to move between rooms), papers presented during concurrent sessions *must not exceed twenty minutes*. If you wish to hear a paper in another session, kindly wait until the five-minute discussion period to move between rooms.

With best wishes for a wonderful Symposium,

Maria Doerfler
Emanuel Fiano
Kyle Smith
Lucas Van Rompay

Overview of Plenary Addresses

- I. **Encountering Eve in Syriac Liturgical Tradition**
Susan Ashbrook Harvey, Brown University
Sunday, 8:00p (Nasher Lecture Hall, Nasher Museum of Art)
- II. **Classical Syriac and the Syriac Churches: A 20th c. History**
Heleen Murre-van den Berg, Leiden University
Monday, 11:30a (Room A)
- III. **Aspects of Linguistic Thought in the Syriac Exegetical Tradition**
Riccardo Contini, University of Naples, "L'Orientale"
Monday, 5:00p (Room A)
- IV. **Scholarship on the Margins: Biblical and Secular Learning in the Work of Jacob of Edessa**
Alison G. Salvesen, University of Oxford
Tuesday, 11:30a (Room A)
- V. **The Chronicle of Michael the Syrian: A Major World History and an Edition Project**
Amir Harrak, University of Toronto
Tuesday, 5:00p (Room A)
- VI. **What Does Mecca Have to Do with Urhoy? Syriac Christianity, Islamic Origins, and the Qur'an: A Study in Intertextuality**
Sidney H. Griffith, Catholic University of America
Wednesday, 11:00a (Room A)
-

Evening Study Session: Projects, Tools, Translations: Monday, 8:00p (Room A)

"Providing access to Syriac manuscripts from the Middle East and India: The current work of the Hill Museum and Manuscript Library"

Columba Stewart and Adam McCollum, Hill Museum and Manuscript Library, Saint John's University, Colledgeville

"The Syriac Reference Portal: An introduction and call for collaborators"

David Michelson, University of Alabama

"Persian Martyr Acts in Syriac: Text and Translation Series (Gorgias Press)"

Adam Becker, New York University

Sunday, June 26

ARRIVAL AND REGISTRATION

2:00 – 5:00p York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)
After 5:00p registration continues at the Nasher Museum of Art.

BUS SERVICE TO THE NASHER

5:00 and 5:15p Buses from the Washington Duke Inn to the Nasher Museum of Art

WELCOME RECEPTION AND BUFFET DINNER

5:30 – 7:30p Nasher Museum of Art

OPENING CEREMONIES

7:30 – 8:00p Great Hall, Nasher Museum of Art

PLENARY LECTURE I – Nasher Lecture Hall, Nasher Museum of Art

Chair: Laura Lieber, Duke University

8:00 – 9:00p **Encountering Eve in Syriac Liturgical Tradition**
Susan Ashbrook Harvey, Brown University

BUS SERVICE FROM THE NASHER

9:15 and 9:30p Buses to the Washington Duke Inn from the Nasher Museum of Art

Monday, June 27

BUS SERVICE TO DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

8:15 and 8:30a Buses from Washington Duke Inn to Duke Divinity

COFFEE & MUFFINS

8:30 – 8:55a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

1-A: THEMES AND TOPICS IN EARLY SYRIAC LITERATURE

Chair: Jeanne-Nicole Saint-Laurent, St. Michael's College

9:00 – 9:25a Craig Morrison, Pontifical Biblical Institute
"When Judas the apostle prays: Intercessory prayer in early Syriac literature"

9:25 – 9:50a James Walters, Princeton Theological Seminary
"Creating a 'people from among the peoples': Aphrahat and the construction of Christian orthodoxy"

9:50 – 10:15a Adam Lehto, University of Toronto
"The natural world in John of Apamea's *Dialogues with Thomas*"

1-B: MONASTICISM AND ASCETICISM, I

Chair: Monica Blanchard, Catholic University of America

9:00 – 9:25a Mar Emmanuel Joseph, Assyrian Church of the East and University of Toronto
"Monastic dress in a *memra* attributed to John bar Penkaye"

9:25 – 9:50a Reyhan Durmaz, Central European University
"Reconstructing the Mount Athos of the East: Christian hierotopy of Ṭur 'Abdin in Late Antiquity"

1-C: SYRIAC IDENTITY, EDUCATION, AND DIASPORA

Chair: Khalid Dinno, University of Toronto

9:00 – 9:25a Nicholas Al-Jeloo, University of Sydney
"From Syriac to Neo-Aramaic and Assyrian: Language, script, and identity in Modern Assyrian inscriptions from Iran"

9:25 – 9:50a Saadi Al-Malih, Ministry of Culture, Kurdistan Regional Government
"The impact of Syriac education and media on Classical Syriac language development in Iraqi Kurdistan"

9:50 – 10:15a Naures Atto, Leiden University
"Challenging the hostages' and orphans' dilemma"

Monday, June 27

COFFEE BREAK

10:15 – 10:35a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

2-A: BETWEEN THE ROMAN EMPIRE & SYRIAC CHRISTIANITY

Chair: David Rensberger, Independent scholar

10:35 – 11:00a Nathanael Andrade, West Virginia University
“A Syriac discourse on Romanness”

11:00 – 11:25a Ilaria Ramelli, Catholic University of the Sacred Heart
“The possible origin of the Addai legend”

2-B: MONASTICISM AND ASCETICISM, II

Chair: Robert Kitchen, Knox-Metropolitan United Church

10:35 – 11:00a Nathan Gibson, Catholic University of America
“Mountains and plains: A Syriac ascetic’s geographical exegesis in the *Memra on Solitaries*”

11:00 – 11:25a Columba Stewart, Hill Museum and Manuscript Library, Saint John’s University, Colledgeville
“Rabbula of Edessa: An ‘observable moment’ in the development of Syriac monasticism?”

2-C: CONTINUITY AND CANON IN SYRIAC LITERATURE

Chair: Alberto Camplani, University of Rome “La Sapienza”

10:35 – 11:00a Kristian Heal, Brigham Young University
“Rewriting, appropriation, and influence in early Syriac literature”

11:00 – 11:25a Adam Becker, New York University
“Retrieving the ruins of Nineveh: Archeology, orientalizing auto-ethnography, and the idea of Syriac literature”

PLENARY LECTURE II – Room A

Chair: Lucas Van Rompay, Duke University

11:30a – 12:30p **Classical Syriac and the Syriac Churches: A Twentieth-Century History**
Heleen Murre-van den Berg, Leiden Univ.

LUNCH

12:30 – 2:00p Refectory, Duke Divinity School

During the lunch hour an exhibition of Syriac manuscripts and early printed books will be on display in the Biddle Rare Book Room (adjacent to the Perkins Library lobby).

Monday, June 27

3-A: THE WORLD OF EPHREM THE SYRIAN

Chair: Kathleen McVey, Princeton Theological Seminary

- 2:00 – 2:25p Jeffrey Wickes, University of Notre Dame
“The poetics of self-presentation in Ephrem’s Hymns on Faith”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Abraham Jacob Thekkeparambil, St. Ephrem Ecumenical Research Institute
“The apostle Simon according to St. Ephrem”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Tenny Thomas, Columbia University and Union Theological Seminary
“Healing through the mysteries of the Eucharist’ in Ephrem”
-

3-B: MONASTICISM AND ASCETICISM, III

Chair: James F. Coakley, Cambridge University

- 2:00 – 2:25p Grigory Kessel, The Philipps University of Marburg
“Syriac monastic anthologies: presentation of a research project”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Joel Walker, University of Washington
“The diver’s quest: Pearl imagery in East-Syriac monastic tradition”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Alessandro Mengozzi, University of Turin
“The Book of Khamis bar Qardaḥe: Preliminary remarks on the history of the text”
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3-C: SYRIAC JURIDICAL LITERATURE

Chair: Maria Doerfler, Duke University

- 2:00 – 2:25p Yifat Monnickendam, Johns Hopkins University
“The sources of the Syro-Roman Lawbook”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Simon Ford, University of Oxford
“‘Chief of the priests’: The bishop in Eastern and Western canon law, AD 400 to 650”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Lev Weitz, Princeton University
“Kinship, law, and exegetical tradition, or: Why can’t an East Syrian marry her cousin?”
-

COFFEE BREAK

- 3:15 – 3:35p York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)
-

Monday, June 27

4-A: BARDAIŞAN IN CONTEXT

Chair: Ute Possek, Gordon College

- 3:35 – 4:00p Alberto Camplani, University of Rome, “La Sapienza”
“Bardaişan’s cosmology and psychology: The witness of Mani, Ephrem, and Diodore and the recent scholarly perspectives”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Thomas McGlothlin, Duke University
“Is Aphrahat’s *Demonstration on the Resurrection* against Bardaişan? Contextualizing *Dem. VIII*”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Robert Morehouse, Catholic University of America
“A common enemy: Theological deviance in Bardaişan’s *Laws of Countries* and Ephrem’s *Hymns against Heresies* and *Prose Refutations*”
-

4-B: ART AND ARCHITECTURE

Chair: Abdo Badwi, University St. Esprit

- 3:35 – 4:00p Karel Innemée, Leiden University
“The wooden doors of Deir al-Surian commissioned by Moses of Nisibis: Their construction and iconography in light of their recent restoration”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Linda Wheatley-Irving, Central European University
“Pesqin Monastery in its Euphrates landscape setting”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Rima Smine, Leiden University
“The tomb of King Abgar: The appropriation of a Sidmara sarcophagus on a Syriac rug”
-

4-C: THE LITURGICAL TRADITION

Chair: Ephrem Ishac, University St. Esprit

- 3:35 – 4:00p Mar Awa Royel, Assyrian Church of the East, Diocese of California
“The *Commentary* of Mar Emmanuel bar Shahhare on the baptismal liturgy”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Jincy Othottil Ulahannan, St. Ephrem Ecumenical Research Institute
“Liturgical theology of St. Mary in the East-Syriac perspective”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Saju Varghese, Orthodox Theological Seminary, Kottayam
“A codicological survey of the liturgical manuscripts of the Orthodox Theological Seminary, Kottayam, India”
-

PLENARY LECTURE III – Room A

Chair: Aaron Butts, Yale University

- 5:00 – 6:00p **Aspects of Linguistic Thought in the Syriac Exegetical Tradition**
Riccardo Contini, University of Naples, “L’Orientale”
-

DINNER

- 6:00 – 8:00p von der Heyden Pavilion, Perkins Library
-

Monday, June 27

EVENING STUDY SESSION – Room A

Chair: Kyle Smith, Duke University

Projects, Tools, Translations:

- 8:00 – 8:40p Columba Stewart and Adam McCollum, Hill Museum and Manuscript Library, Saint John's University, Collegeville
"Providing access to Syriac manuscripts from the Middle East and India: The current work of the Hill Museum and Manuscript Library"
- 8:40 – 9:05p David Michelson, University of Alabama
"The Syriac Reference Portal: An introduction and call for collaborators"
- 9:05 – 9:30p Adam Becker, New York University
"Persian Martyr Acts in Syriac: Text and Translation Series (Gorgias Press)"

BUS SERVICE FROM DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

9:30 and 9:45p Buses from Duke Divinity to Washington Duke Inn

Tuesday, June 28

BUS SERVICE TO DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

8:15 and 8:30a Buses from Washington Duke Inn to Duke Divinity

COFFEE & MUFFINS

8:30 – 8:55a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

5-A: LANGUAGE, SCRIPT, AND COMPUTATIONAL MODELS

Chair: Kristian Heal, Brigham Young University

- 9:00 – 9:25a Aaron Butts, Yale University
“Taking the temperature of Syriac: A corpus study of Greek loanwords in Classical Syriac”
- 9:25 – 9:50a George A. Kiraz, Beth Mardutho
“Remarks on the graphotactics of Old Syriac”
- 9:50 – 10:15a Eric Ringger, Brigham Young University
“Computational models of Syriac and how to train them”
-

5-B: EVAGRIUS OF PONTUS AND HIS RECEPTION IN SYRIAC

Chair: Columba Stewart, Hill Museum and Manuscript Library, St. John’s University, Collegeville

- 9:00 – 9:25a Robin Darling Young, University of Notre Dame
“Problems in the Syriac translation of the *Letters of Evagrius*”
- 9:25 – 9:50a Charles Stang, Harvard University
“Evagrius’ grammarology: Writing in the *Great Letter*”
- 9:50 – 10:15a Maria Doerfler, Duke University
“Socializing Evagrius: The case of Philoxenus of Mabbug’s *Letter to Patricius*”
-

5-C: EAST-SYRIAC ASCETIC LITERATURE

Chair: Joel Walker, University of Washington

- 9:00 – 9:25a Dennis Hou, Independent scholar
“The flying dolphin in the mirror: Simon of Taibutheh’s medico-mystical laughter”
- 9:25 – 9:50a Nestor Kavvadas, University of Tübingen
“... and we do not turn aside from the way of the Interpreter’. Joseph Hazzaya’s *Treatise on the Divine Providence*: Argumentative strategies and literary sources”
- 9:50 – 10:15a Steven Payne, Harvard University
“‘The anticipated resurrection’: John of Dalyatha and biblical interpretation in the East-Syriac ascetic tradition”
-

Tuesday, June 28

COFFEE BREAK

10:15 – 10:35a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

6-A: MARA BAR SERAPION'S LETTER

Chair: Mark Goodacre, Duke University

10:35 – 11:00a David Rensberger, Independent scholar
"The grammar of the *Letter of Mara bar Serapion*
and other early Syriac texts"

11:00 – 11:25a Kathleen McVey, Princeton Theological Seminary
"Looking a gift horse in the mouth: Revisiting
the *Letter of Mara bar Serapion to his son*"

6-B: THE ACTS OF THE PERSIAN MARTYRS

Chair: Adam Becker, New York University

10:35 – 11:00a Kyle Smith, Duke University
"Constantine and the Christians of Persia,
reconsidered"

11:00 – 11:25a Adam McCollum, Hill Museum and Manuscript
Library, St. John's University, Colledgeville
"Poetized hagiography: The martyrdoms of
Jacob of Bet Lapaṭ and Tahmazgard in story
and song"

6-C: BIBLICAL LANGUAGE AND READING

Chair: Riccardo Contini, University of Naples, "L'Orientale"

10:35 – 11:00a Mark Meyer, Capital Bible Seminary
"Genitive constructions in the Peshitta of
Exodus"

11:00 – 11:25a James F. Coakley, Cambridge University
"The marking of questions in the Peshitta New
Testament"

PLENARY LECTURE IV – Room A

Chair: Melvin Peters, Duke University

11:30a – 12:30p **Scholarship on the Margins: Biblical and Secular
Learning in the Work of Jacob of Edessa**
Alison G. Salvesen, University of Oxford

LUNCH

12:30 – 2:00p Refectory, Duke Divinity School

*During the lunch hour an exhibition of Syriac manuscripts
and early printed books will be on display in the Biddle Rare
Book Room (adjacent to the Perkins Library lobby).*

Tuesday, June 28

7-A: BIBLICAL INTERPRETATION

Chair: Carl Griffin, Brigham Young University

- 2:00 – 2:25p Mark Bilby, University of Virginia and Point Loma Nazarene University
“Luke 23:39-43 in early Syriac reception”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Paul Feghali, Independent scholar
“The Book of Job in the Syriac tradition and particularly in Isho‘dad of Merv”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Stephen Ryan, Dominican House of Studies
“The Numbers Commentary of Dionysius bar Šalibi”
-

7-B: EPHREM THE SYRIAN AND JACOB OF SERUG

Chair: Susan Ashbrook Harvey, Brown University

- 2:00 – 2:25p Erin Galgay, Duke University
“The sacrifice of Cain in the commentaries of Ephrem and Ambrose”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Mary Hansbury, Independent scholar
“Love as an exegetical principle in Jacob of Serug”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Robert Kitchen, Knox-Metropolitan United Church
“A poetic life: *Vita* of Jacob of Serug by Sa‘id bar Sabuni”
-

7-C: RELIGIOUS AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTERACTIONS

Chair: Hidemi Takahashi, University of Tokyo

- 2:00 – 2:25p Steve Cochrane, University of the Nations
“Re-assessment of Muslim views of Christian monasteries, with particular reference to the early ninth century”
- 2:25 – 2:50p Jan van Ginkel, Leiden University
“A new manuscript of Job of Edessa’s *Book of Treasures* under the spotlight”
- 2:50 – 3:15p Ute Possekel, Gordon College
“Christological debates in eighth-century Harran: Leo of Harran and Eliya the Bishop”
-

COFFEE BREAK

- 3:15 – 3:35p York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)
-

Tuesday, June 28

8-A: HAGIOGRAPHY: TEXT AND GENRE

Chair: Jacob Thekkeparambil, St. Ephrem Ecumenical Research Institute

- 3:35 – 4:00p Emanuel Fiano, Duke University
“The Syriac version of the *Passio Cypriani et Justinae*”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Jeanne-Nicole Saint-Laurent, Saint Michael’s College
“Relic donation and theft in Syriac hagiography”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Monica Blanchard, Catholic University of America
“Timothy, metropolitan of Gargar (d. 1143 or 1169), and the monastic founders of Scetis”
-

8-B: SYRIAC CHRISTIANITY AND JUDAISM

Chair: Eric Meyers, Duke University

- 3:35 – 4:00p Naomi Koltun-Fromm, Haverford College
“Early Syriac Fathers on Jerusalem”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Stephanie Bolz, University of Michigan
“A Jewish adjuration formula in three Syriac magic bowls”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Yonatan Moss, Yale University
“Moses bar Kepha and Saadia Gaon: The Syriac background for Saadia’s philosophy and exegesis”
-

8-C: SIXTH- & SEVENTH-CENTURY EAST SYRIAC LITERATURE

Chair: Robin Darling Young, University of Notre Dame

- 3:35 – 4:00p George Bevan, Queen’s University
“A displaced page in Nestorius’ *Liber Heraclidis*”
- 4:00 – 4:25p Said Hayaati, University of Applied Science and Technology
“The theology of Paul the Persian”
- 4:25 – 4:50p Andrew Platt, Catholic University of America
“The testing of God: Mar Babai the Great on divine impassibility”
-

PLENARY LECTURE V – Room A

Chair: Herman Teule, Radboud University Nijmegen and Catholic University of Louvain

- 5:00 – 6:00p **The Chronicle of Michael the Syrian: A Major World History and an Edition Project**
Amir Harrak, University of Toronto
-

RECEPTION AND DINNER

- 6:00 – 7:00p Reception sponsored by Gorgias Press for all Symposium participants, York Reading Room
- 7:00 – 9:00p Dinner, Faculty Commons, West Union Building
-

BUS SERVICE FROM DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

- 9:00 and 9:15p Buses from Duke Divinity to Washington Duke Inn

Wednesday, June 29

BUS SERVICE TO DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

8:15 and 8:30a Buses from Washington Duke Inn to Duke Divinity

COFFEE & MUFFINS

8:30 – 8:55a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

9-A: CONSTRUCTIONS OF THE 'OTHER'

Chair: Joel Marcus, Duke Divinity School

9:00 – 9:25a Christine Shepardson, University of Tennessee
"Meaningful meetings: Constructing linguistic difference in and around late antique Antioch"

9:25 – 9:50a Cynthia Villagomez, Winston-Salem State University
"The presence and representation of black Africans in Syriac literature and culture"

9-B: SYRIAC SONG

Chair: George A. Kiraz, Beth Mardutho

9:00 – 9:25a Tala Jarjour, New York University Abu Dhabi
"Syriac chant as music culture"

9:25 – 9:50a Shawqi Talia, Catholic University of America
"*Dilillol*: Neo-Aramaic lullabies from Christian Mesopotamia"

9-C: CHRISTIANS AND MUSLIMS

Chair: Alessandro Mengozzi, University of Turin

9:00 – 9:25a Thomas Carlson, Princeton University
"Syriac patriarchs and Muslim rulers in the fifteenth century"

9:25 – 9:50a Rifaat Ebied, University of Sydney
"Dionysius bar Šalibi's works in the Mingana Collection of Syriac and Arabic manuscripts, with special emphasis on his polemical *Treatise against the Muslims*"

COFFEE BREAK

9:50 – 10:05a York Reading Room (Gray Building, 2nd floor)

Wednesday, June 29

10-A: RESPONSES TO THE 'OTHER'

Chair: Emanuel Fiano, Duke University

- 10:05 – 10:30a Alberto Rigolio, University of Oxford
"From 'Socrates and Xanthippe' to 'Socrates and his wife': Ignorance or deliberate modification in Syriac translations of Greek pagan literature?"
- 10:30 – 10:55a Jaisy Joseph, Harvard University
"The clash of worldviews on the Malabar Coast"
-

10-B: LITERATURE OF THE SYRIAC RENAISSANCE

Chair: Ebrahim Moosa, Duke University

- 10:05 – 10:30a Hidemi Takahashi, University of Tokyo
"Barhebraeus, *Cream of Wisdom, Books of First Philosophy and Theology*: Preliminary observations"
- 10:30 – 10:55a Herman Teule, Radboud University Nijmegen and Catholic University of Louvain
"The theme of language in Christian-Muslim discussions"
-

10-C: TURKS AND MONGOLS IN SYRIAC CHRONICLES

Chair: Amir Harrak, University of Toronto

- 10:05 – 10:30a Khalid Dinno, University of Toronto
"The Turks and Mongols in the contemporary Syriac chronicles"
- 10:30 – 10:55a Andy Hilken, Ghent University
"There are Turks, and then there are Turks: The description of the Turks (Book XIV) in the *Chronicle* of Michael the Great and its Armenian counterparts"
-

PLENARY LECTURE VI – Room A

Chair: Rifaat Ebied, University of Sydney

- 11:00a – 12:00p **What Does Mecca Have to Do with Urhoy? Syriac Christianity, Islamic Origins, and the Qur'an: A Study in Intertextuality**
Sidney Griffith, Catholic University of America
-

CLOSING CEREMONIES, BUSINESS MEETING, AND LUNCH

- 12:00 – 1:30p Refectory, Duke Divinity School
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BUS SERVICE FROM DUKE DIVINITY SCHOOL

- 1:30p Buses from Duke Divinity to Washington Duke Inn

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The Sixth North American Syriac Symposium at Duke University was made possible through the generous support of the following sponsors:

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